

Factsheet

trans4num Danish NBS site is exploring changes in crop rotation towards more perennial grass crops for reducing environmental impacts of crop production and with the purpose of using the grass biomass for biorefinery purposes. This change ensures a new circular nutrient retention scheme and prioritized N crop-rotation systems including more perennial grass crops with longer growth season and adoption potentials to weather extremes and climate change, and combination with local protein supply chains.

Agroecology, circular agriculture and the role of nature-based solutions

To understand nature based solutions we need to have a whole-systems approach to agriculture and foods systems development based on traditional knowledge, alternative agriculture and local food systems .

Tommy Dalgaard, Morten Graversgaard, Nele Lohrum presenting an overview of the Danish context regarding NBS and agroecology studies.

Agroecology, circular agriculture and the role of nature-based solutions

trans4num is a four-year project funded under the Zero Pollution call as an EU-China international cooperation action on nature-based solutions (NBS) for nutrient management in agriculture.

trans4num ambition is to broadly enhance the NBS implementation in Europe with an integrative and tested multi-level approach, in dialogue with academic partners, practice partners and societal stakeholders.

